

1 **The allometry of brain size in Euarchontoglires: clade-specific patterns and their impact on**
2 **encephalization quotients**

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TEASER TEXT

Our study examines the scaling relationships between brain mass and body mass for Euarchontoglires (primates, treeshrews, colugos, rodents, and lagomorphs). This study provides the largest euarchontogliran dataset of endocast data and adds enough data to calculate the first brain-body scaling equation for Scandentia. Additionally, previously inferred scaling patterns for lagomorphs are now found to be closer to rodents. Brain-body size scaling equations are also used for calculating encephalization quotients (EQ), but mammal-wide equations do not effectively control for body mass in comparing brain masses. Using clade-specific patterns, new EQ equations should allow for effective comparison of brain sizes in analyses of euarchontoglirans at varying taxonomic scales.

44 **Abstract**

45 The timing and nature of evolutionary shifts in the relative brain size of Primates has been
46 extensively studied. Less is known, however, about the scaling of the brain to body size in their
47 closest living relatives, i.e., among other members of Euarchontoglires (Dermoptera, Scandentia,
48 Lagomorpha, Rodentia). Ordinary least squares (OLS), reduced major axis (RMA) and
49 phylogenetic generalized least squares (PGLS) regressions were fitted to the largest
50 euarchontogliran dataset of brain and body mass, comprising 715 species. Contrary to previous
51 inferences, lagomorph brain sizes (PGLS slope = 0.465; OLS slope = 0.593) scales relative to
52 body mass similarly to rodents (PGLS = 0.526; OLS = 0.638), and differently than primates
53 (PGLS = 0.607; OLS = 0.794). There is a shift in the pattern of the scaling of the brain in
54 Primates, with Strepsirrhini occupying an intermediate stage similar to Scandentia but different
55 from Rodentia and Lagomorpha, while Haplorhini differ from all other groups in the OLS and
56 RMA analyses. The unique brain-body scaling relationship of Primates among Euarchontoglires
57 illustrates the need for clade-specific metrics for relative brain size (i.e., encephalization
58 quotients; EQ) for more restricted taxonomic entities than Mammalia. We created clade-specific
59 regular and phylogenetically adjusted EQ equations at superordinal, ordinal, and subordinal
60 levels. When using fossils as test cases, our results show that generalized mammalian equations
61 underestimate the encephalization of the stem lagomorph *Megalagus turgidus* in the context of
62 lagomorphs, overestimate the encephalization of the stem primate *Microsyops annectens* and the
63 early euprimate *Necrolemur antiquus*, but provide similar EQ values as our new strepsirrhine-
64 specific EQ when applied to the early euprimate *Adapis parisiensis*.

65

66 **Key words:** biological scaling, body size, brain size, comparative anatomy, endocasts,
67 neurobiology

68
69 One of the defining characteristics of modern primates is their relatively large brain size
70 compared to other mammalian orders (Martin 1990). Primates have historically received
71 significant attention with respect to the question of how their brain size scales in relation to body
72 size (e.g., Count 1947; Gould 1975; Lande 1979; Clutton-Brock and Harvey 1980; Bronson
73 1981; Shea 1983; Armstrong 1985; Martin and Harvey 1985; Marino 1998; Sherwood et al.
74 2008; Boddy et al. 2012; Smaers et al. 2012, 2021; Holekamp et al. 2013; Burger et al. 2019).
75 Within the order Primates, hominoids (Hominoidea) are particularly encephalized, both in the
76 larger context of Mammalia and compared to the much less encephalized and smaller bodied
77 strepsirrhines (Strepsirrhini). This association between body size and degree of encephalization
78 leads to Primates having the highest slope value in ordinary least square regression analyses of
79 brain mass against body mass among any of the mammalian orders (Burger et al. 2019).
80 However, to fully understand evolutionary trends that define the primate brain, it is necessary to
81 place the scaling of the primate brain within a phylogenetic context. This exercise is two-fold: on
82 the one hand, it is important to explore how brain-to-body scaling relationships differ at a
83 subordinal level within Primates, while on the other hand it is important to put primate data into
84 the larger context of their close, non-primate relatives.

85 While there is a long history of the study of relative brain size in primates, the consensus
86 around the broader phylogenetic context within which these data should be assessed has changed
87 relatively recently (Murphy et al. 2001). Literature from only a few decades ago treated
88 “insectivorans” as a good model for primitive states for the primate brain—this was true, for

89 example, with respect to the classic and oft-reanalyzed compilation of quantitative data on
90 primate brains by Stephan et al. (1970, 1981). However, modern phylogenetic studies (e.g. Foley
91 et al. 2023) position eulipotyphlan “insectivorans” as relatively distant to primates. Instead,
92 Primates are broadly considered to be members of the superorder Euarchonta (together with the
93 orders Dermoptera and Scandentia; Waddell et al. 1999), and Euarchonta is understood to be
94 most closely related to the superorder Glires (Rodentia + Lagomorpha) within the greater
95 grouping of Euarchontoglires (Murphy et al. 2001; Foley et al. 2023).

96 Recent molecular analyses have supported both Dermoptera (Mason et al. 2016; Zhang et al.
97 2019; Foley et al. 2023) and Sundatheria (Dermoptera + Scandentia; Olson et al. 2005; Upham et
98 al. 2019) as the sister group of Primates. However, dermopterans are only known from 2 species,
99 which makes it problematic to delve into the relationship between brain mass and body mass at
100 an ordinal level. In the case of Scandentia, the present paper is the first consideration of
101 allometric relationships between brain and body mass for this group. Smaers et al. (2021)
102 inferred a value for Scandentia from an ancestral state reconstruction analysis, but that was based
103 on only 5 taxa, all of them tupaiines. Relative brain size has been more intensively studied in
104 rodents (e.g., Count 1947; Mace et al. 1981; Mace and Eisenberg 1982; Pilleri et al. 1984;
105 Hafner and Hafner 1984; Towe and Mann 1992; Bernard and Nurton 1993; Mann and Towe
106 2003; Matějů et al. 2016; Burger et al. 2019; Bertrand et al. 2021), but much less for lagomorphs.
107 Burger et al. (2019) reported that the regression slope values for rodent and lagomorph
108 regressions of brain mass on body mass were notably different. In their analysis, rodents had a
109 slope value of 0.64, but lagomorphs were reported to have a slope value of 0.75 (Burger et al.
110 2019). This result implies that the brains in lagomorphs would scale more similarly to primates
111 (slope value of 0.79; Burger et al. 2019) than they would to rodents, which would be surprising

112 for a group that is not generally thought of as having comparatively encephalized larger
113 members.

114 The calculation of allometric regressions describing brain scaling for the various
115 euarchontoglriran groups is also of particular relevance for the calculation of encephalization
116 quotients (EQ; Jerison 1973; Supplementary Data SD1). Although sometimes criticized (e.g.,
117 Deacon 1990; Begun and Kordos 2004; Schoenemann 2006; Deaner et al. 2007; Gilbert and
118 Jungers 2017), the calculation of metrics related to EQs for fossil taxa remains a critically
119 important part of assessing brain size evolution through time in Primates and other orders (e.g.,
120 Boddy et al. 2012; Ni et al. 2019; Bertrand et al. 2022; Silcox et al. 2023). To date, the most
121 commonly used equations for calculation of EQ in fossil Euarchontoglires are based on general
122 mammalian samples (i.e., Jerison 1973; Eisenberg 1981). However, some authors have taken the
123 approach of studying relative brain size evolution using EQs calculated from more restricted
124 samples, which might provide a better framework for studying variation and evolution of relative
125 brain size within the context of a particular group. For example, Pilleri et al. (1984) developed a
126 rodent-specific equation that has recently been used for the calculation of EQs in many fossil
127 rodent studies (Bertrand and Silcox 2016; Bertrand et al. 2016, 2017, 2018, 2019a). More
128 recently, Grabowski et al. (2016) and Ni et al. (2019) developed primate-specific equations based
129 on PGLS regressions of endocranial volume vs. body mass, and Ni et al. (2019) coined the term
130 “phylogenetic encephalization quotient” (PEQ). Further, Bertrand et al. (2021) developed a PEQ
131 equation for their own sample of sciuroid rodents and extinct closest relatives, Püschel et al.
132 (2021) also used their own equation for PEQ using extant and extinct hominoids, and Bertrand et
133 al. (2022) conceived their own equation of PEQ for a sample of extinct placental mammals.

134 In the present study we aim to: 1) analyze the allometry of brain mass to body mass across
135 Euarchontoglires and at lower taxonomic levels; 2) examine the patterns in relative brain size
136 variation among and within major evolutionary lineages; and 3) generate clade-specific
137 encephalization quotient equations. The goal of generating clade-specific EQ equations is to
138 minimize error and allow authors to tailor their research questions to narrower taxonomic
139 frameworks. The current work therefore considers patterns of allometric scaling in all
140 euarchontogliran orders and probes the question of how best to use that information to study the
141 evolution of relative brain size through time.

142

143 **Materials and methods**

144 *The studied sample.*

145 We acquired estimates of brain size and body size for 715 species of Euarchontoglires
146 (Supplementary Data SD2). In our analyses, we used data from previously published literature
147 (Bertrand and Silcox 2016; Bertrand et al. 2017, 2018, 2019a, 2021; Burger et al. 2019; López-
148 Torres et al. 2020; Smaers et al. 2021; Lang et al. 2022). In all cases, when data originated from
149 endocranial volumes (cm³), they were converted to brain mass (g) by dividing the endocranial
150 volume by 1.036 (Stephan et al., 1981). For details about original sources of data, see
151 Supplementary Data SD2. In the process of combining datasets, we were careful to avoid
152 duplicating entries. In some cases, new data for particular species were combined with data from
153 previous literature to generate new average values. For rodents, we combined the datasets from
154 Burger et al. (2019), Bertrand and Silcox (2016), Bertrand et al. (2018, 2021), and Lang et al.
155 (2022). For lagomorphs, we combined the datasets from Burger et al. (2019), López-Torres et al.
156 (2020), and Smaers et al. (2021). For primates, we combined Burger et al.'s (2019) and Lang et

157 al.'s (2022) datasets. For scandentians, we combined Burger et al.'s (2019) and San Martin
158 Flores et al.'s (2018) datasets. The new scandentian sample ($n = 14$) allows us to generate the
159 first regression lines for brain vs. body mass for this order of mammals. The brain size data for
160 dermopterans were obtained from Lang et al. (2022) and include both extant species; the body
161 mass data were taken from Stafford and Szalay (2000). Although it is fundamentally
162 uninformative to generate a regression line from only 2 points, the dermopteran species were still
163 included in the calculations for the regression lines for Euarchonta and Euarchontoglires.

164 Following the total number of species in different mammalian orders by Burgin et al. (2018),
165 the present study samples 100% of currently recognized dermopteran species (2/2), 58% of
166 currently recognized scandentian species (14/24), 47.88% of currently recognized primate
167 species (248/518), 31.63% of currently recognized lagomorph species (31/98), and 16.46% of
168 currently recognized rodent species (420/2552). Only extant taxa were included in this analysis.
169 The main reason for the exclusion of extinct taxa is that uncertainty in body mass estimates for
170 fossils would lead to very large amounts of error around the calculated regression lines, making
171 it difficult to interpret any differences as being a product of relative brain size vs. uncertainty in
172 the underlying data. Also, because there is a temporal effect in brain size in several mammalian
173 orders (Jerison 1973; Silcox et al. 2010; Orliac and Gilissen 2012; Yao et al. 2012; Bertrand et
174 al. 2019a, 2022), simultaneously analyzing fossils with extant taxa has the potential of conflating
175 temporal patterns with scaling relationships that exist within particular groups at a given moment
176 in evolutionary time. However, it is a fair concern that these temporal shifts could make the
177 scaling relationships calculated here an inaccurate representation of those that would have
178 applied at other points in the evolution of euarchontogirans. Investigating these complexities is
179 beyond the scope of the current analysis.

180 No research was conducted on live animals.

181 *Analysis.*

182 The scaling of brain size with body size has typically been characterized by a power law (Snell
183 1892; Dubois 1898; Jerison 1973), where:

$$184 \quad (\text{Brain mass}) = \alpha(\text{Body mass})^\beta$$

185 and α and β are constants representing the intercept and slope, respectively. This relationship
186 becomes linear by log transforming both sides of the equation:

$$187 \quad \log(\text{Brain mass}) = \log(\alpha) + \beta \cdot \log(\text{Body mass})$$

188 Ordinary least squares (OLS), reduced major axis (RMA), and phylogenetic generalized least
189 squares (PGLS) regressions were fitted to our data. We used all 3 approaches to allow for
190 comparison to previous analyses and to enable the calculation of both regular EQs and PEQs.
191 Bootstrapped estimates of OLS and RMA regression slopes and intercepts were generated for
192 each taxonomic grouping based on 10,000 random resampling iterations using the Statistics101
193 software package (<http://www.statistics101.net/>). The PGLS analysis was conducted by
194 incorporating an extensively sampled, time-scaled mammalian phylogeny (Upham et al. 2019);
195 of the total of 715 taxa, 696 taxa could be included based on their presence in the Upham et al.
196 (2019) analysis. All regression parameters were simultaneously estimated with phylogenetic
197 signal in the residual error as Pagel's lambda (Pagel 1999; Revell 2010) using the `phylolm`
198 function in the R package 'phylolm' (Tung Ho and Ané, 2014). Regression lines of the 3 types
199 were calculated at multiple taxonomic levels: supraordinal (Euarchonta, Glires, and
200 Euarchontoglires), ordinal (Primates, Scandentia, Rodentia, and Lagomorpha), and subordinal
201 (Strepsirrhini and Haplorhini).

202

203 *Calculation of significance.*

204 *P*-values are strongly dependent on sample size and relate to an arbitrarily chosen alpha level. In
205 this study, rather than making determinations of statistical significance using standard *P*-values
206 consistent with traditional hypothesis testing, we chose to estimate what the difference in slope
207 and intercept values is likely to be between taxonomic groups (see discussion in Smith 2020). To
208 do this we used random resampling with replacement to generate resampling distributions of the
209 difference between taxonomic groupings in slope and intercept values, also based on 10,000
210 resampling iterations. We used these resampling distributions to generate 95% confidence
211 intervals, which is the interval that comprises 95% of the resampled differences between the 2
212 taxonomic groupings compared. Standard deviations and 95% confidence intervals for the
213 slopes, intercepts, and differences between taxonomic groupings were generated from the
214 resampling distributions. We use standard deviation of the resampled distribution as the standard
215 error of the bootstrap estimate (i.e., slope, intercept, or difference).

216

217 *New EQ equations.*

218 In this study, we propose new clade-specific EQs (Table 1), following the model suggested by
219 Pilleri et al. (1984) specifically for rodents, which has been previously used in studies focusing
220 on fossil rodent endocasts (Bertrand and Silcox 2016; Bertrand et al. 2016, 2018, 2019b). These
221 equations are based on more constrained samples, instead of general mammalian samples as in
222 Jerison (1973) or Eisenberg (1981). The new equations are derived from the OLS and the PGLS
223 regression equations. Additionally, in this study we are using a few fossil specimens as test cases
224 for the new EQs. In particular, we use the stem lagomorph *Megalagus turgidus* (FMNH UC
225 1642; López-Torres et al. 2020), the stem primate *Microsyops annectens* (UW 14559; Silcox et

226 al. 2010), the adapoid primate *Adapis parisiensis* (NHM M 1345; Harrington et al. 2016), and
227 the omomyoid primate *Necrolemur antiquus* (MaPhQ 289; Harrington et al. 2020) to allow us to
228 consider the value of taxonomically constrained EQ equations. Brain mass and body mass data
229 for these species are provided in Table 2.

230

231 *Institutional abbreviations.*

232 FMNH UC—University of Chicago collection, Field Museum of Natural History, Chicago, IL,
233 USA; MaPhQ—Muséum d’Histoire Naturelle Victor Brun, Montauban, France; NHM—Natural
234 History Museum, London, UK; UW—University of Wyoming, Laramie, WY, USA.

235

236 **Results**

237 Results for the ordinary least squares (OLS) analysis are shown in Tables 3 and 4; the results for
238 the phylogenetic generalized least squares (PGLS) analysis are shown in Tables 5 and 6; and the
239 results for the reduced major axis (RMA) analysis are shown in the Supplementary Data SD3.

240 The calculated regression lines are shown at the supraordinal level (Euarchonta, Glires, and
241 Euarchontoglires; Fig. 1), ordinal level (Primates, Scandentia, Rodentia, and Lagomorpha; Fig.
242 2), and subordinal level (Strepsirrhini and Haplorhini; Fig. 3). Fig. 4 combines different
243 regression lines in 1 graph to better visualize the comparison between slopes and intercepts.

244

245 *Ordinary least squares analysis.*

246 Our results show that the brains of rodents, lagomorphs, and scandentians scale similarly with
247 respect to body mass (i.e., have similar slopes; 0.638, 0.594, and 0.604, respectively; Fig. 2B-D).
248 The 95% confidence intervals (95% CI) for each of the comparisons among these 3 taxonomic

249 groupings included zero. The bootstrap estimates of the differences in slope for the 3
250 comparisons ranged from -0.034 to 0.044 (Table 4). Our reanalysis of the Burger et al. (2019)
251 data set (i.e., excluding the new data used in the present analysis) failed to recover their results
252 with respect to lagomorphs (i.e., a slope of 0.75), suggesting that the appearance of a difference
253 is based on an error in their analysis of their data.

254 When assessed at an ordinal level, the brains of primates (slope = 0.794; Fig. 2A) do
255 show evidence of scaling differently from other euarchontoglires orders (Fig. 4A). None of the
256 95% CIs for any of the comparisons with Primates included zero. This same pattern was
257 observed for Haplorhini, which exhibit a high slope value (slope = 0.723; Fig. 3A). Interestingly,
258 the 95% CIs for comparisons of Strepsirrhini with both Rodentia and Lagomorpha excluded
259 zero, while the comparisons with Haplorhini and Scandentia included zero. This pattern of
260 results suggests that while the slope value for haplorhines is likely higher than other members of
261 Euarchontoglires, strepsirrhines (slope = 0.679) occupy an intermediate scaling pattern between
262 non-primate Euarchontoglires and haplorhines. These findings were largely mirrored by the
263 results of RMA regression (Supplementary Data SD3), with the exception of the Strepsirrhini-
264 Rodentia comparison.

265 The intercepts for these various regressions (Table 3) show that hypothetically small
266 haplorhines would have larger brains than similarly small strepsirrhines (Fig. 3). However, the
267 overall primate regression intersects with the Y axis at a lower value (-1.133) than the haplorhine
268 (-0.834) and the strepsirrhine (-0.932) regressions do—a by-product of having large-brained,
269 large-bodied anthropoids in the primate sample, which tilt the regression line in a way that
270 increases the slope and decreases the intercept when strepsirrhines and haplorrhines are
271 combined (Fig. 2A). Small rodents would also be expected to have smaller brains than small

272 strepsirrhines and small haplorhines, based on the estimate of the rodent intercept (-1.050; Fig.
273 2C). But when looking at the general primate regression, small rodents would have larger brains
274 than small primates (Fig. 4A)—again, is a by-product of the high slope of the overall primate
275 regression. The highest intercept is observed in scandentians (-0.821), with the hypothetical
276 small scandentians having larger brains than even small haplorhines. This high intercept is
277 probably due to the fact that scandentians have both a shallow slope (0.604; similar to the
278 lagomorph slope, 0.594) and that they have slightly larger brains than lagomorphs of similar
279 body mass (Fig. 4A).

280

281 *Phylogenetic generalized least squares analysis.*

282 The PGLS analysis showed a strong phylogenetic signal (i.e., $\lambda \geq 0.875$ for all groupings). The
283 main difference between the values calculated in the OLS and PGLS analyses is that PGLS
284 gives, in the case of this study, systematically lower slope values and higher intercept values than
285 OLS (Table 5). This contrast is particularly pronounced in primates and lagomorphs, because in
286 these 2 groups there is a strong clade-specific pattern in body mass—for example, among
287 haplorhines, the different major clades (i.e., tarsioids, platyrrhines, cercopithecoids, hominoids)
288 are each fairly constrained in their size range, with only a small degree of overlap between these
289 groups. Because this pattern is also related to relative brain mass, controlling for this pattern has
290 the effect of substantially decreasing the slope in the regression lines generated by PGLS.

291 Only the comparisons between Euarchonta and Glires, Primates and Glires, and Primates
292 and Lagomorpha excluded zero in their 95% CIs. Within primates, the slope of the regression
293 line analyzed ordinally (0.607) is intermediate in value between the strepsirrhine (0.614) and
294 haplorrhine (0.578) slopes. Scandentians are more similar to primates in having a relatively

295 higher slope value (0.580) than rodents (0.526) or lagomorphs (0.465; Fig. 4A-B). In comparing
296 the PGLS and OLS slope values for the various orders the greatest similarity is observed for
297 Scandentia (0.580 vs. 0.604, respectively), likely as a consequence of the fact that there is little
298 phylogenetic effect on body mass in Scandentia (Fig. 2). Both the largest and smallest species of
299 scandentians are tupaiines (*Tupaia everetti*, 249.5 g; *Dendrogale murina*, 45 g; Sargis, 2002).
300 The slope for Glires (0.524) is intermediate between the rodent (0.526) and lagomorph (0.465)
301 slopes, although it is very similar to the rodents. It is likely that the slope for Glires is so similar
302 to rodents because the sample of Glires is mostly composed of rodents (421 rodents vs 31
303 lagomorphs). Also, the range of body mass of lagomorphs is contained within the range of body
304 mass for rodents (Figure 1C), so it is not expected that lagomorphs would shift the numbers
305 substantially, as they might have if lagomorphs were clustered at one extreme or the other. The
306 euarchontan slope (0.603) is also intermediate between the primate (0.607) and the scandentian
307 (0.580) slopes but very close in value to the primate slope. That is a similar situation to the one
308 seen with Glires; the euarchontan sample is largely made up of primates (248 primates, 14
309 scandentians, 2 dermopterans), and the scandentian and dermopteran ranges of body mass are
310 within that of strepsirrhines (Figure 1B). Finally, the slope for Euarchontoglires (0.540) has a
311 value similar to those calculated for non-primate Euarchontoglires.

312 As in OLS, the intercepts of the PGLS regressions show that hypothetically small
313 haplorhines would have larger brains than small strepsirrhines. However, in the PGLS analysis,
314 the overall primate regression intersects with the Y axis between the haplorhine and the
315 strepsirrhine intercepts. Contrary to the finding in the OLS analysis, the highest intercept in
316 PGLS, at an ordinal level, is observed for lagomorphs instead of scandentians (Figure 4B).

317 Another important difference between the OLS and PGLS regressions is that in the OLS
318 analysis there are more groups that could be considered different based on the 95% CI values in
319 terms of scaling patterns, but PGLS fails to find most of these differences. In pairwise
320 comparisons PGLS only finds clear differences in scaling between Euarchonta and Glires,
321 between Primates and Glires, and between Primates and Rodentia (Table 6).

322

323 **Discussion**

324 Our results differ from the conclusion of Burger et al. (2019) that the lagomorph brain scales
325 more similarly to primates—instead our results indicate that lagomorphs show a scaling
326 relationship closer to that seen in rodents with respect to body mass (Fig. 4A-B). This correction
327 highlights the uniqueness of primates in a euarchontoglriran context. This is further supported in
328 the OLS analysis, where primates are the only order of Euarchontoglires with the 95%
329 confidence intervals for differences in slope that do not include zero.

330 Strepsirrhines have similar OLS slopes to both haplorhines and scandentians, differing
331 from those of rodents and lagomorphs. However, the scandentian slope differs from haplorhines,
332 making strepsirrhines an apparently intermediate stage between other primates and non-primate
333 euarchontoglrirans. On the other hand, the confidence intervals for the slope in the PGLS
334 analysis overlap among many more ordinal groupings. However, primates stand out even in the
335 PGLS analysis for being the only order with a confidence interval for their slope that does not
336 overlap with rodents. Consequently, the fact that primates appear to have a unique brain-body
337 scaling relationship in the context of Euarchontoglires (supported by both the OLS and the PGLS
338 analyses) further illustrates the necessity for clade-specific regular EQs and phylogenetic EQs for
339 more restricted taxonomic entities than Mammalia.

340 A recent analysis (Smaers et al. 2021) examined allometric scaling relationships across
341 Mammalia, identifying particular points in the mammalian tree where they inferred grade shifts
342 had occurred. In their analysis, several groups analyzed here were reconstructed as part of the
343 ancestral mammalian grade (Scandentia, Lagomorpha, Dermoptera, squirrel-related clade,
344 Tarsioidea) based on their allometric scaling relationships not being found to have differed from
345 the relationship calculated for the common mammalian ancestor, with a primitive PGLS slope of
346 0.51. However, this slope lies outside the 95% confidence interval for Euarchontoglires,
347 Euarchonta, Primates, and Strepsirrhini calculated here (Table 5). As such, our analysis would
348 suggest that a grade shift might have happened earlier in the evolution of this clade than their
349 analysis suggests. In particular, the contrast between Primates and Glires found in all analyses
350 suggests an ordinal level shift for Primates, contrasting with inferred changes occurring only
351 within primate subgroups in the result of Smaers et al. (2021). Possible explanations for this
352 contrast are the notably stronger sampling of both Scandentia and Rodentia here, which allowed
353 for a refinement of previous estimates, but also the direct inclusion of fossils in Smaers et al.
354 (2021). However, these inferences require testing using fossil specimens that allow for a more
355 direct window into such grade shifts.

356

357 *Encephalization quotients.*

358 The encephalization quotient (EQ) is a widely used index of brain size scaled to body size
359 (Jerison, 1979). As noted above, some of the most commonly used EQ equations in the field of
360 paleoprimateology are Jerison's (1973) and Eisenberg's (1981), even though they are based on
361 generalized mammalian samples. However, the use of EQs has been criticized for poorly
362 modelling brain scaling relationships in fossil primates (Gilbert and Jungers 2017), as well as for

363 not being a good predictor of cognitive abilities (Deaner et al. 2007). Although imperfect, no
364 alternative has been suggested to EQs for comparing brain sizes in animals of different body
365 masses that is not also problematic. For example, taking a narrow allometric approach (as
366 suggested by Gilbert and Jungers 2017) is very prone to error being introduced by
367 inconsistencies in body mass estimation, and does not offer a clear solution for making
368 comparisons to fossil taxa outside the modern range of variation (White et al. 2022). While we
369 agree with Smaers et al. (2021) that making comparisons between particular brain regions offers
370 a much richer understanding of brain size evolution than looking at relative overall size (see for
371 example Bertrand et al. 2019b), such an approach is limited in dealing with fossils because only
372 certain brain regions can be isolated on endocasts. We would also argue that, in light of the high
373 physiological cost of maintaining brain tissue, considering relative brain size has fundamental
374 merit in discussions of brain evolution, whether or not it is an accurate proxy for measures of
375 cognition. As such, EQs continue to serve as useful tools, and merit further work to overcome
376 identified problems. The growing availability of brain and body mass data for Euarchontoglires
377 allows us to elaborate subordinal, ordinal, and supraordinal EQ equations, which may allow for
378 more meaningful comparisons relevant to some evolutionary questions than are possible with
379 general mammalian equations, and may solve some of the problems that have been identified
380 with EQs such as a lack of independence from body mass (Begun and Kordos 2004; Gilbert and
381 Jungers 2017). Our results show that in the OLS regression analyses the slopes generally
382 increase and the intercepts decrease the higher we go in taxonomic level within Euarchontoglires
383 (see also Martin 1990). Therefore, in order to avoid overestimation and underestimation of EQs
384 in animals with extreme body masses, it is preferable to use the most taxonomically specific EQ
385 possible. In fact, Pilleri et al. (1984) already elaborated an OLS-based EQ equation specific to

386 rodents that has been used in recent studies on the brain evolution of rodents (Bertrand and
387 Silcox 2016; Bertrand et al. 2016, 2017, 2018, 2019a). Other groups within Euarchontoglires are
388 worth exploring with respect to this approach.

389 López-Torres et al. (2020) described the first virtual endocast of a fossil lagomorph and
390 provided EQs for both extant lagomorphs and a specimen of *Megalagus turgidus* (FMNH UC
391 1642), a stem lagomorph. The body mass of *M. turgidus* was calculated by López-Torres et al.
392 (2020) using the width of the occipital condyles, which is argued to be one of the most reliable
393 measures of body mass estimation in lagomorphs ($r^2 = 0.957$; Moncunill-Solé et al. 2015).
394 Because of the lack of a lagomorph-specific EQ, the authors used Jerison's (1973) and
395 Eisenberg's (1981) equations. The present OLS-based lagomorph-specific equation (Table 1)
396 provides a higher EQ estimate (0.53) than those calculated with generalized mammalian
397 equations (Jerison's EQ = 0.32; Eisenberg's EQ = 0.40). This equation also provides higher
398 estimates for living lagomorphs than previously calculated (i.e., López-Torres et al. 2020). Here,
399 the critical point is that calculating the group-specific value makes it clear that in the lagomorph
400 context *Megalagus* was more encephalized than previously thought, with a brain only
401 approximately half the size expected rather than approximately one-third. Our Glires-specific EQ
402 for *Megalagus* gives a very similar result (0.55) to the lagomorph-specific EQ. However, the
403 Euarchontoglires-specific EQ for *Megalagus* drops to 0.29, even lower than the generalized
404 mammalian EQs of Jerison (1973) and Eisenberg (1981). This is most certainly due to the effect
405 of adding primates, and in particular highly-encephalized anthropoids. These differing values
406 highlight the importance of making a choice of EQ equation that is relevant to the evolutionary
407 question being asked, and that EQ calculations need to be put in a specific taxonomic
408 framework.

409 With respect to primates, Grabowski et al. (2016) pioneered using PGLS regressions to
410 calculate EQs instead of using the traditional OLS. They developed a primate-specific EQ,
411 although based on endocranial volume rather than brain mass. Recently, Ni et al. (2019)
412 expanded upon analyses of Grabowski et al. (2016) by publishing EQ equations specific for
413 anthropoids, platyrrhines, and catarrhines based on PGLS regressions (i.e., PEQ; Ni et al., 2019).
414 Here we complement these equations with primate-, strepsirrhine-, and haplorhine-specific
415 equations based on OLS (regular EQ) and PGLS (phylogenetic EQ or PEQ) using brain mass
416 (see Table 1 for the specific EQ and PEQ equations). It is worth noting that EQs and PEQs are
417 not directly comparable, so future studies may benefit from calculating both. For example,
418 whereas an $EQ = 1$ always means that the brain size of an animal is exactly the brain size
419 expected for an animal of its size, this is not necessarily true when $PEQ = 1$ because the PGLS
420 analysis corrects the position of the regression line based on phylogenetic effect (if there is one).
421 As such, PGLS estimates have the benefit of including a metric (EQ) that allows for some degree
422 of comparability with past analyses, while also providing information within the context of a
423 particular analysis that reflects our understanding of phylogeny (PEQ).

424 Here we use 3 early primates (a plesiadapiform, an adapoid, and an omomyoid) as test
425 cases for our new primate equations. *Microsyops annectens* is a microsyopid plesiadapiform
426 from the middle Eocene of North America known from a substantively complete cranium (UW
427 12362; Silcox et al. 2010, 2020) with a range of EQs between 0.25 and 0.38 using Jerison's
428 (1973) equation, and between 0.31 and 0.49 using Eisenberg's (1981) equation. The range of
429 EQs is due to the fact that Silcox et al. (2010) calculated several body mass estimates, including
430 a cranial length insectivoran equation (Thewissen and Gingerich 1989), a cranial length
431 horizontal primate PGLS equation (Silcox et al. 2009), a cranial length generic primate equation

432 (Martin 1990), and an upper molar area equation (Gingerich et al. 1982). Using our OLS-based
433 primate-specific equation, *Microsyops* yields a lower range of EQ estimates (0.15-0.25) than
434 those resulting from Jerison's (1973) and Eisenberg's (1981) equations. The euarchontan-
435 specific equation gives the same EQ values as the primate-specific equation. The
436 Euarchontoglires-specific equation provides more similar values to those of Jerison's (1973)
437 equation, with EQs in the range of 0.22-0.37. These results accentuate the fact that *M. annectens*
438 had an extremely small brain for a primate but was quite similar to the stem lagomorph *M.*
439 *turgidus* when the EQs of both are calculated using a Euarchontoglires-specific equation.

440 *Adapis parisiensis* is an adapid adapoid from the late Eocene of Europe. Jerison's (1973)
441 equation provides an EQ of 0.65 and Eisenberg's (1981) an EQ of 0.86 based on a very complete
442 cranium (NHM M1345; Harrington et al., 2016). Harrington et al. (2016) calculated the body
443 mass of *A. parisiensis* using the euarchontan ectal facet equation (Yapuncich et al. 2015). The
444 relationships of adapoids are somewhat controversial, with conflicting views about whether
445 adapoids are haplorhines (Wortman 1903-1904; Gingerich 1973, 1984, 2012, 2015; Gingerich
446 and Schoeninger 1977; Rasmussen and Simons 1988, 1992, 1994; Simons 1989; Simons and
447 Rasmusen 1989; Rasmussen 1990, 1994; Bloch et al. 1997; Franzen et al. 2009) or strepsirrhines
448 (Gregory 1920; Hoffstetter 1977; Beard et al. 1988; Dagosto 1988; Kay et al. 1997; Seiffert et al.
449 2009; Williams et al. 2010; Gilbert and Maiolino 2015). Current large-scale cladistic analyses
450 tend to place adapoids in the strepsirrhine side of the primate tree (Ni et al. 2016; Gunnell et al.
451 2018; Seiffert et al. 2018), so the consensus leans towards considering them as most likely stem
452 strepsirrhines. Here, we follow the current consensus and consider adapoids stem strepsirrhines
453 and consequently apply the strepsirrhine-specific EQ equation to *Adapis*. This equation yields an
454 EQ of 0.62, similar to that derived from Jerison's (1973) equation. The primate and the

455 euarchontan-specific equations give similar results ($EQ_{\text{Primates}} = 0.44$; $EQ_{\text{Euarchonta}} = 0.45$), and the
456 Euarchontoglires-specific equation provides a similar EQ to the strepsirrhine-specific and
457 Jerison's (1973) equations (0.65).

458 Harrington et al. (2020) published a virtual endocast of the omomyoid, *Necrolemur*
459 *antiquus*, a late Eocene European microchoerid, based on a very complete cranium (MaPhQ
460 289). Jerison's (1973) equation yields an EQ of 0.68 for *Necrolemur*, and Eisenberg's (1981) an
461 EQ of 1.04. Harrington et al. (2020) calculated the body mass of *N. antiquus* using a cranial
462 length equation (Martin 1990). Unlike adapoids, the phylogenetic relationships of omomyoids
463 are much less controversial and they are mostly regarded as haplorhines, with a closer
464 relationship to modern tarsiers (e.g., Ni et al. 2016). The haplorhine-specific equation gives a
465 much lower EQ (0.43) than that provided by the generalized mammalian equations, whereas the
466 primate and euarchontan equations give more intermediate values ($EQ_{\text{Primates}} = 0.59$; $EQ_{\text{Euarchonta}}$
467 $= 0.62$). The Euarchontoglires-specific EQ yields a more similar value (0.91) to that given using
468 Eisenberg's (1981) equation. The results from both *A. parisiensis* and *N. antiquus* highlight the
469 importance of selecting an EQ equation based on the research question being asked. In particular,
470 for *N. antiquus*, the very low haplorhine EQ value emphasizes the contrast in relative brain size
471 between this fossil taxon and living members of Haplorhini. So, *N. antiquus* was quite
472 encephalized for an early Tertiary primate, but actually not very encephalized for a modern
473 haplorrhine, as might be expected for a stem taxon.

474 To conclude, the present study explores the scaling relationships between body mass and
475 brain mass in Euarchontoglires. To our knowledge, this is the first instance that the scaling
476 relationships between brain mass and body mass have been reported for Scandentia (Fig. 2B), a
477 group that has been underrepresented in previous studies for lack of brain data. Our results also

478 show that the brain of lagomorphs scales with respect to body mass similarly to rodents, and very
479 differently than Primates (Fig. 4A-B; contra Burger et al., 2019).

480 Generating clade-specific EQs provides some insight into issues that have been raised
481 with the general mammalian equations of Jerison (1973) and Eisenberg (1981). As shown by
482 Gilbert and Jungers (2017; see also Begun and Kordos 2004) these EQ equations do an imperfect
483 job at controlling for body mass. A critical reason for this issue is that the brain allometries in the
484 various subgroups of mammals vary greatly, making clade-specific EQs necessary. In other
485 words, the relationship between EQ and body mass observed by those authors stems from using a
486 scaling equation (either Jerison's or Eisenberg's) that does not correctly control for body mass
487 because it does not accurately reflect scaling relationships of the mammalian subsample of
488 interest (i.e., Primates, Rodentia, Lagomorpha, etc.). Therefore, clade-specific EQs will be more
489 appropriate when the research questions being asked concern a more taxonomically narrow
490 sample. The use of Jerison's (1973) and Eisenberg's (1981) equations might be appropriate for
491 research questions that concern a broad sample of mammals, particularly distantly related
492 mammals. Choosing Jerison's (1973) or Eisenberg's (1981) equations for a taxonomically
493 narrow sample (like Rodentia or Primates) will maximize the overestimations and
494 underestimations of relative brain size for members with more extreme body sizes (either small
495 or large, respectively). Eisenberg's (1981) equation gives closer EQ values than Jerison's (1973)
496 does for rodents to those yielded by Pilleri et al.'s (1984) equation, which is a rodent-specific
497 OLS-based equation. This makes Eisenberg's (1981) equation a more appropriate choice for
498 rodents over Jerison's (1973). However, Jerison's (1973) equation yields similar EQ values to
499 those given by the strepsirrhine-specific EQ, making Jerison's (1973) equation more appropriate
500 for strepsirrhines over Eisenberg's (1981). This contrast highlights the reality that neither is a

501 generally preferred option across all scales of comparisons. In sum, clade-specific equations
502 (Pilleri et al. 1984; Grabowski et al. 2016; Ni et al. 2019; Bertrand et al. 2021; this paper) should
503 be given preference whenever the research question focuses on a particular mammalian group,
504 and generalized mammalian equations (Jerison 1973; Eisenberg 1981) are only appropriate for
505 broad comparative mammalian samples.

506

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512

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514 SLT and MTS contributed to Conceptualization and Project Administration; SLT, OCB, ŁF-F,
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529

530 **Conflict of Interest**

531 None declared

532

533 **Data Availability**

534 All data are available in the Supplementary Data.

535

536

537 **Supplementary data**

538 Supplementary data are available at *Journal of Mammalogy* online.

539 **Supplementary Data SD1.** Text explaining how encephalization quotients are calculated.

540 **Supplementary Data SD2.** Body mass and brain mass data for 715 euarchontoglriran

541 species, sorted by order. Sample sizes are included as specifically as the literature allows,

542 sometimes including ranges. Data have been extracted from the ‘Direct source’. Direct sources

543 often include original sources where the data came from in the respective manuscripts. When a

544 direct source is listed as ‘Combined’, it means that data from several original sources (sometimes

545 including newly generated data) have been combined.

546 **Supplementary Data SD3.** Results from the reduced major axis (RMA) analysis. This

547 file includes slope and intercept data for several taxonomic levels in Euarchontoglires using

548 RMA and pair-wise comparisons between regression parameters of different taxonomic groups

549 of Euarchontoglires. Values in red denote coverage probabilities that do not include zero. N =

550 number of species; SD = standard deviation; CI = confidence interval; CP = coverage
551 probability.

552 **Supplementary Data SD4.** References used for tables in Supplementary Data SD2.

553 **Supplementary Data SD5.** Bivariate plots of log brain mass versus log body mass for
554 Strepsirrhini (Figure 3B) with *Adapis parisiensis* indicated with a black star. OLS regression
555 represented as a dashed line; PGLS regression represented as a solid line. Note that the body
556 mass and brain mass values for *A. parisiensis* have not been taken into account when calculating
557 the regression lines.

558 **Supplementary Data SD6.** Bivariate plots of log brain mass versus log body mass for
559 Strepsirrhini (Figure 3A) with *Necrolemur antiquus* indicated with a black star. OLS regression
560 represented as a dashed line; PGLS regression represented as a solid line. Note that the body
561 mass and brain mass values for *N. antiquus* have not been taken into account when calculating
562 the regression lines.

563 **Supplementary Data SD7.** Bivariate plots of log brain mass versus log body mass for
564 Primates (Fig. 2A) with *Microsyops annectens*, *Adapis parisiensis*, and *Necrolemur antiquus*
565 indicated with black stars. OLS regression represented as a dashed line; PGLS regression
566 represented as a solid line. Note that the body mass and brain mass values for *M. annectens*, *A.*
567 *parisiensis*, and *N. antiquus* have not been taken into account when calculating the regression
568 lines. BM \uparrow , high body mass estimate; BM \downarrow , low body mass estimate.

569 **Supplementary Data SD8.** Bivariate plots of log brain mass versus log body mass for
570 Lagomorpha (Fig. 2D) with *Megalagus turgidus* indicated with a black star. OLS regression
571 represented as a dashed line; PGLS regression represented as a solid line. Note that the body

572 mass and brain mass values for *M. turgidus* have not been taken into account when calculating
573 the regression lines.

574 **Supplementary Data SD9.** Bivariate plots of log brain mass versus log body mass for
575 Euarchonta (Fig. 1B) with *Microsyops annectens*, *Adapis parisiensis*, and *Necrolemur antiquus*
576 indicated with black stars. OLS regression represented as a dashed line; PGLS regression
577 represented as a solid line. Note that the body mass and brain mass values for *M. annectens*, *A.*
578 *parisiensis*, and *N. antiquus* have not been taken into account when calculating the regression
579 lines. BM↑, high body mass estimate; BM↓, low body mass estimate.

580 **Supplementary Data SD10.** Bivariate plots of log brain mass versus log body mass for
581 Glires (Fig. 1C) with *Megalagus turgidus* indicated with a black star. OLS regression
582 represented as a dashed line; PGLS regression represented as a solid line. Note that the body
583 mass and brain mass values for *M. turgidus* have not been taken into account when calculating
584 the regression lines.

585 **Supplementary Data SD11.** Bivariate plots of log brain mass versus log body mass for
586 Euarchontoglires (Fig. 1A) with *Microsyops annectens*, *Adapis parisiensis*, *Necrolemur*
587 *antiquus*, and *Megalagus turgidus* indicated with black stars. OLS regression represented as a
588 dashed line; PGLS regression represented as a solid line. Note that the body mass and brain mass
589 values for *M. annectens*, *A. parisiensis*, *N. antiquus*, and *M. turgidus* have not been taken into
590 account when calculating the regression lines. BM↑, high body mass estimate; BM↓, low body
591 mass estimate.

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FIGURE LEGENDS

Fig. 1. Bivariate plots of log brain mass versus log body mass for 715 euarchontoglriran species. Points are color coded by order, except for Primates, which are divided into the suborders Haplorhini and Strepsirrhini. Best fit lines are shown for the ordinary least squares (OLS; dashed) and phylogenetic generalized least squares (PGLS; solid) regressions. (A) Data for the entire sample, with the best fit line for Euarchontoglires (OLS slope = 0.809, intercept = -1.344; PGLS slope = 0.540, intercept = -0.670); (B) Data for members of Euarchonta (Primates, Dermoptera, Scandentia; OLS slope = 0.805, intercept = -1.177; PGLS slope = 0.603, intercept = -0.724); (C) Data for members of Glires (Rodentia, Lagomorpha; OLS slope = 0.635, intercept = -1.044; PGLS slope = 0.524, intercept = -0.774).

Fig. 2. Bivariate plots of log brain mass versus log body mass for individual euarchontoglriran orders. Best fit lines are shown for the ordinary least squares (OLS; dashed) and phylogenetic generalized least squares (PGLS; solid) regressions. (A) Data for Primates, with points color coded by suborder. The best fit lines are for all Primates (OLS slope = 0.794, intercept = -1.133; PGLS slope = 0.607, intercept = -0.607); (B) Data for Scandentia (OLS slope = 0.604, intercept = -0.821; PGLS slope = 0.580, intercept = -0.778); (C) Data for Rodentia (OLS slope = 0.638, intercept = -1.050; PGLS slope = 0.526, intercept = -0.779); (D) Data for Lagomorpha (OLS slope = 0.594, intercept = -0.931; PGLS slope = 0.465, intercept = -0.581).

Fig. 3. Bivariate plots of log brain mass versus log body mass for Primates by suborder. Best fit lines are shown for the ordinary least squares (OLS; dashed) and phylogenetic generalized least squares (PGLS; solid) regressions. (A) Data for Haplorhini (OLS slope = 0.723, intercept = -0.834; PGLS slope = 0.578, intercept = -0.468); (B) Data for Strepsirrhini (OLS slope = 0.679; intercept = -0.932; PGLS slope = 0.614, intercept = -0.687).

Fig. 4. Bivariate plots of log brain mass versus log body mass for all 715 euarchontoglires. (A) Data are color coded by order, best fit lines are shown for the ordinary least squares regressions for each order except for Dermoptera. Primates slope = 0.794, intercept = -1.133; Scandentia slope = 0.604, intercept = -0.821; Rodentia slope = 0.638, intercept = -1.050; Lagomorpha slope = 0.594, intercept = -0.931. (B) Data are color coded by order, best fit lines are shown for the Phylogenetic generalized least squares regressions for each order except for Dermoptera. Primates slope = 0.607, intercept = -0.607; Scandentia slope = 0.580, intercept = -0.778; Rodentia slope = 0.526, intercept = -0.779; Lagomorpha slope = 0.465, intercept = -0.581. (C) Data are color coded by superorder, best fit lines are shown for the ordinary (OLS; dashed) and phylogenetic generalized least squares (PGLS; solid) regressions for Euarchonta (Primates, Dermoptera, Scandentia; OLS slope = 0.805, intercept = -1.177; PGLS slope = 0.603, intercept = -0.724); and Glires (Rodentia, Lagomorpha; OLS slope = 0.635, intercept = -1.044; PGLS slope = 0.524, intercept = -0.774).

Table 1. Formulae to calculate the expected brain mass (E_c) for a given body mass (BM) for specific taxonomic groups. The EQ and PEQ are calculated by dividing the actual brain mass by the E_c given in this table. The equations are formulated the following way: $10^{\text{intercept}} * (\text{body mass})^{\text{slope}}$.

	E_c for EQ	E_c for PEQ
Euarchontoglires	$0.045 * BM^{0.809}$	$0.214 * BM^{0.540}$
Euarchonta	$0.067 * BM^{0.805}$	$0.189 * BM^{0.603}$
Glires	$0.090 * BM^{0.635}$	$0.168 * BM^{0.524}$
Rodentia	See Pilleri et al. (1984)	$0.166 * BM^{0.526}$
Lagomorpha	$0.117 * BM^{0.594}$	$0.262 * BM^{0.465}$
Scandentia	$0.151 * BM^{0.604}$	$0.167 * BM^{0.580}$
Primates	$0.074 * BM^{0.794}$	$0.247 * BM^{0.607}$
Strepsirrhini	$0.117 * BM^{0.679}$	$0.206 * BM^{0.614}$
Haplorhini	$0.146 * BM^{0.723}$	$0.341 * BM^{0.578}$

Table 2. Brain mass and body mass data (in grams) for selected taxa of fossil Euarchontoglires.

Order	Family	Species	Specimen number	Brain mass	Body mass	Source
Lagomorpha	Megalagidae	<i>Megalagus turgidus</i>	FMNH UC 1642	6.72	2325.01	López-Torres et al. (2020)
Primates	Microsyopidae	<i>Microsyops annectens</i>	UW 12362	5.62	1358—2568	Silcox et al. (2010)
Primates	Adapidae	<i>Adapis parisiensis</i>	NHM M1345	8.39	1103	Harrington et al. (2016)
Primates	Microchoeridae	<i>Necrolemur antiquus</i>	MaPhQ 289	2.36	144	Harrington et al. (2020)

Table 3. Allometries for log10 brain size versus log10 body size across different taxonomic levels within Euarchontoglires based on bootstrap estimates of ordinary least square (OLS) regression parameters. Abbreviations: *n* = number of sampled species; *r* = correlation coefficient; SD = standard deviation; CI = confidence interval.

Taxon	<i>n</i>	<i>r</i>	Slope	SD	95% CI		Intercept	SD	95% CI	
					Lower end	Upper end			Lower end	Upper end
Euarchontoglires	715	0.959	0.809	0.009	0.791	0.826	-1.344	0.021	-1.386	-1.303
Euarchonta	264	0.963	0.805	0.011	0.783	0.827	-1.177	0.037	-1.251	-1.105
Glires	451	0.962	0.635	0.008	0.619	0.652	-1.044	0.019	-1.082	-1.008
Rodentia	420	0.959	0.638	0.010	0.619	0.657	-1.050	0.021	-1.089	-1.008
Lagomorpha	31	0.955	0.594	0.037	0.517	0.668	-0.931	0.117	-1.160	-0.693
Scandentia	14	0.964	0.604	0.048	0.502	0.692	-0.821	0.099	-1.004	-0.608
Primates	248	0.959	0.794	0.014	0.769	0.822	-1.133	0.047	-1.228	-1.044
Strepsirrhini	63	0.958	0.679	0.019	0.645	0.719	-0.932	0.053	-1.045	-0.837
Haplorhini	185	0.954	0.723	0.018	0.687	0.759	-0.834	0.066	-0.961	0.702

Table 4. Pairwise comparisons of bootstrap estimates of differences among Euarchontoglires in ordinary least square (OLS) regression parameters. Abbreviations: SD = standard deviation; CI = confidence interval. Asterisks = likely to be different.

Taxon	Slope bootstrap difference	SD	95% CI		Intercept bootstrap difference	SD	95% CI	
			Lower end	Upper end			Lower end	Upper end
Euarchonta—Glires	0.169*	0.042	0.143	0.197	-0.133*	0.042	-0.215	-0.051
Rodentia—Lagomorpha	0.044	0.039	-0.031	0.123	-0.119	0.120	-0.364	0.114
Rodentia—Scandentia	-0.034	0.102	-0.138	0.055	0.228*	0.102	0.044	0.445
Lagomorpha—Scandentia	0.010	0.153	-0.111	0.126	0.110	0.153	-0.187	0.416
Primates—Glires	0.158*	0.050	0.128	0.191	-0.088	0.050	-0.190	0.007
Primates—Rodentia	0.156*	0.050	0.125	0.189	-0.084	0.050	-0.185	0.011
Primates—Lagomorpha	0.200*	0.128	0.123	0.283	-0.204	0.128	-0.468	0.042
Primates—Scandentia	0.190*	0.108	0.103	0.294	-0.313*	0.108	-0.542	-0.114
Strepsirrhini—Haplorhini	0.044	0.085	-0.010	0.094	0.097	0.085	-0.060	0.272
Strepsirrhini—Scandentia	0.074	0.113	-0.018	0.182	-0.111	0.113	-0.348	0.093
Strepsirrhini—Rodentia	0.040*	0.056	0.002	0.083	0.117	0.056	-0.002	0.218
Strepsirrhini—Lagomorpha	0.085*	0.130	0.003	0.170	-0.002	0.130	-0.267	0.246
Haplorhini—Scandentia	0.112*	0.138	0.010	0.248	0.003	0.138	-0.302	0.246
Haplorhini—Rodentia	0.085*	0.069	0.042	0.125	0.215	0.069	0.083	0.356
Haplorhini—Lagomorpha	0.130*	0.137	0.048	0.216	0.093	0.137	-0.184	0.357

Table 5. Allometries for log10 brain size versus log10 body size across different taxonomic levels within Euarchontoglires based on bootstrap estimates of phylogenetic generalized least square (PGLS) regression parameters. Abbreviations: n = number of sampled species; λ = Pagel's lambda (tree transformation that measures phylogenetic signal); SD = standard deviation; CI = confidence interval.

Taxon	n	R^2	λ	Slope	SD	95% CI		Intercept	SD	95% CI	
						Lower end	Upper end			Lower end	Upper end
Euarchontoglires	696	0.766	0.898	0.540	0.011	0.518	0.561	-0.670	0.067	-0.811	-0.540
Euarchonta	254	0.779	0.882	0.603	0.022	0.561	0.644	-0.724	0.096	-0.911	-0.538
Glires	442	0.779	0.882	0.524	0.013	0.499	0.549	-0.774	0.088	-0.949	-0.611
Rodentia	413	0.784	0.875	0.526	0.013	0.501	0.550	-0.779	0.097	-0.967	-0.593
Lagomorpha	29	0.784	0.875	0.465	0.084	0.295	0.628	-0.581	0.272	-1.092	-0.083
Scandentia	14	0.784	0.875	0.580	0.114	0.364	0.803	-0.778	0.250	-1.262	-0.313
Primates	238	0.784	0.875	0.607	0.022	0.566	0.650	-0.607	0.114	-0.833	-0.385
Strepsirrhini	60	0.725	0.915	0.614	0.044	0.527	0.701	-0.687	0.193	-1.053	-0.316
Haplorhini	178	0.725	0.915	0.578	0.029	0.518	0.635	-0.468	0.162	-0.793	-0.154

Table 6. Pairwise comparisons of bootstrap estimates of the differences in phylogenetic generalized least square (PGLS) regression parameters among Euarchontoglires. Abbreviations: SD = standard deviation; CI = confidence interval. Asterisks = likely to be different.

Taxon	Slope Bootstrap Difference	SD	95% CI		Intercept Bootstrap Difference	SD	95% CI	
			Lower end	Upper end			Lower end	Upper end
Euarchonta—Glires	0.079*	0.025	0.031	0.128	0.050	0.126	-0.197	0.286
Rodentia—Lagomorpha	-0.060	0.085	-0.226	0.106	0.198	0.272	-0.301	0.708
Rodentia—Scandentia	-0.054	0.115	-0.279	0.161	0.000	0.269	-0.543	0.522
Lagomorpha—Scandentia	-0.115	0.142	-0.386	0.168	0.197	0.366	-0.484	0.901
Primates—Glires	0.083*	0.026	0.031	0.132	0.167	0.144	-0.133	0.441
Primates—Rodentia	0.082*	0.026	0.034	0.134	0.172	0.147	-0.105	0.450
Primates—Lagomorpha	-0.142	0.088	-0.309	0.027	0.026	0.296	-0.534	0.616
Primates—Scandentia	0.027	0.116	-0.211	0.247	0.172	0.276	-0.365	0.708
Strepsirrhini—Haplorhini	-0.036	0.053	-0.143	0.067	0.219	0.230	-0.234	0.666
Strepsirrhini—Scandentia	-0.043	0.123	-0.281	0.197	-0.080	0.323	-0.720	0.578
Strepsirrhini—Rodentia	0.088	0.046	-0.002	0.184	0.092	0.214	-0.309	0.511
Strepsirrhini—Lagomorpha	0.149	0.091	-0.020	0.330	-0.106	0.316	-0.704	0.509
Haplorhini—Scandentia	0.007	0.118	-0.213	0.245	0.299	0.310	-0.313	0.888
Haplorhini—Rodentia	0.052	0.032	-0.012	0.117	0.311	0.188	-0.056	0.668
Haplorhini—Lagomorpha	0.113	0.090	-0.067	0.288	0.114	0.319	-0.513	0.741

